

Navigating the Transition: Experiences of Senior High School Social Science Teachers in Teaching Alternative Learning System Completers

Aljohn B. Anticristo ✉

*Graduate School Program, Master of Arts in Education-Teaching Social Studies Student,
Holy Cross of Davao College, Philippines*

Abstract

Student learning variability is deeply concerning. The teachers' experiences in handling student variability were explored. Using phenomenological design, I interviewed ten purposively selected Social Studies teachers of ALS completers, and I thematized the data. As a result, I viewed UDL as insufficient. Designing flexible teaching approach does not directly based on the persisting learner variability. It needs to go through reviewing the academic gaps and instructional adjustments. Besides, flexible teaching approach goes up to the level of implementation and valuing. Consequently, teachers may importantly review student learning gap and their own instructional adjustment before designing flexible teaching approaches; implement and value differentiated and supportive pedagogical activities. Future research may use mediating analysis and EFA to examine how academic gaps and differentiated pedagogical designs mediate the relationship between learner variability, flexible teaching approaches, and UDL-driven pedagogical design, using the sub-themes from this study as variable indicators.

Keywords: *Navigating the transition, experiences in teaching alternative learning system completers, senior high school, social science teachers.*

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Introduction

The Problem and Its Scope

In the global educational landscape, teachers' difficulty in handling students from non-formal education settings has become a significant problematic situation within classroom practice (Education International, 2025).

In India, teachers working with community-based and adult literacy learners describe the struggle of reconciling diverse trajectories within formal classrooms. In South Africa, educators face tensions between standardized curricula and the varied realities of township and rural students. In Brazil, teachers engaging youth from alternative programs experience unsettling shifts in classroom rhythm that demand constant adaptation (Guerra & Ubayubay, 2025).

In the Philippine context, the difficulty of teachers in handling students from non-formal education pathways particularly those transitioning from the Alternative Learning System (ALS) is likewise a pressing concern. As noted by Guerra and Ubayubay (2025), teachers face gaps in foundational skills that require additional instructional support.

The consequences of teacher difficulty in handling students from non-formal education backgrounds are considerable, affecting both instructional effectiveness and learner outcomes (Education International, 2025). These concerns strengthen the rationale for conducting this study.

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Significance of Study

This research helps to achieve sustainable development goal 4 by ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education. It can facilitate the development of resilient, lifelong learners by assisting teachers in incorporating ALS completers in regular classes as specified in the DepEd mission, vision and goal. It also resonates with the mission and vision of the HCDC in that it encourages responsive, transformative, and learner-centered education practice to accommodate the marginalized learners as they move through non-formal education pathways.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to explore the experiences of senior high school social science teachers handling alternative learning system (ALS) completers. Specifically, I sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of Senior High School social science teachers teaching ALS completers on dealing with learning gaps and adjustment issues among completers?
2. What are their experiences in implementing differentiated and supportive pedagogies in teaching ALS completers?
3. What are their teaching experiences that define it as navigate as challenging and fulfilling endeavor?

Theoretical Lens

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is an instructional methodology that anticipates the needs of a variety of learners by planning instruction. UDL emphasizes flexible strategies rather than requiring learners to adapt to a fixed curriculum, minimizing barriers to learning and offering equal learning opportunities. At the fundamental level, UDL acknowledges that learners have different ways of interacting with content, processing information, and expressing what they have learned (Rose & Meyer, 2002).

Conceptual Paradigm

Figure 1. Universal Design for Learning Theory by Rose & Mayer, 2002

Assumption

In this study, I assumed that the difficulties faced by Social Science teachers in handling ALS completers are influenced not only by learner variability but also by the learning environment and the design of assessment and evaluation practices. I further assumed that flexible teaching approaches, guided by the principles of Universal Design for Learning (UDL), must consider these multiple factors: learner differences, accessible and supportive classroom environments, and proper assessment strategies to effectively facilitate inclusive instruction, enhance teacher responsiveness, and promote equitable learner outcomes.

Methodology

In this chapter, I presented the methodology specifically research design, participants and sampling and research instruments. I also presented the data collection, data analysis, and trustworthiness of the study.

Research Design

In this study, I employed a phenomenological approach to describe the experiences of my study participants. I am convinced that phenomenology was appropriate in my study since it seeks to interpret the shared experiences of a group to understand the essence of a phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). I applied this approach to capture the teachers' experiences and in handling ALS learners.

Locale of Study

I conducted the conversation with my study participants in 3 schools belonging to 1 cluster in the division of Davao City. Such cluster is located in a place mixed of rural and urban areas. It is specifically located in the southern part of the city.

Sample and Sampling Technique

I used purposive sampling technique to select 10 participants. These participants had at least three years of teaching experience, meeting the inclusion criteria for the study, while less experienced teachers were excluded. This sample size aligns with Creswell's (1998) recommendation of 3 to 15 participants for phenomenological research.

Data Gathering Technique

In this research, I employed semi structured interviews to capture extensive information on the experiences of Senior High School Social Science teachers dealing with Alternative Learning System (ALS) completers. The interviews were recorded by consent, tape-recorded, word-for-word transcription, and thematically analyzed to come up with major patterns and themes.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed through thematic analysis, which included transcription, coding, and theme development (Creswell, 2013). The interview data were transcribed, scrutinized and analyzed to determine patterns, similarities and differences. These were collated into themes and summarized in tables. The responses were similar and designated, and new themes were noted as well. Triangulation of interview responses and peer review by research experts enhanced the reliability of the findings.

Trustworthiness

In building trustworthiness about my study, the information obtained during my research work was processed with the highest precision and ensured that it was accurately reflected in the recordings. I followed the standards of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability identified by Lincoln and Guba (2000).

The credibility was established by triangulation of data, bracketing of researcher bias, correct transcription, and validation of the interview data by the participants (Creswell, 2013). And I also strengthened by asking the endorsement of HCDC-SMILE (Society of Moral Integrity and Legal Ethics), meaning that the study is regarded as rigorous and ethically appropriate by the institution. To ensure transferability, I gave clear and descriptive explanations of the research context, participants, and methods. I also ensured dependability through systematic documentation of the research process and the use of an inquiry audit to confirm the consistency of the findings (Connelly, 2016). And I strengthened confirmability through the utilization of audit trails, reflexive practices, member checking and the use of relevant literature to ensure that the findings were grounded in the participants' responses rather than researcher bias (Polit & Beck, 2014).

Results

In this chapter, I developed a modified paradigm based on the information I gathered. While I acknowledged the Importance of UDL, I learned that it is limited. I discerned that learning is incomplete when action is up to designing only. Beside that I convene that a design can never be appropriate if there is no adequate assessment. Below are the details of the result of my study.

Figure 2. Modified Paradigm

In the UDL perspective, it is assumed that in the educational setting learners' variability is a reality. Students differ in their backgrounds, abilities, interests, motivations, learning styles, and life circumstances. Recognizing these variabilities shift the focus from seeing differences as problems to viewing them as normal and valuable aspects of learning. Based on the assertion of UDL that learner variabilities challenge designing flexible teaching approach. Nevertheless, in my exploration with teachers experiences I reflected that the link is not a direct process from learner variability to flexible teaching approach. I was convinced that the process might go through reviewing the student learning gap and the teaching adjustment concern.

Reviewing Learning Gap and Teaching Adjustment Concern

Acknowledging learner variability requires first understanding the specific challenges that students bring into the classroom. When it comes to ALS completers, it is the teachers who pointed to the fact that there must be evaluation of learning gaps and issues with adjustment before they can engage in meaningful instruction. Such learners may have entered senior high school with diverse backgrounds and circumstances in life which determines their approach in learning activities. From the teachers shared experiences, one key idea emerged: academic gaps and instructional adjustments.

Academic Gaps and Instructional Adjustments. When I spoke with the interviewees, one of the teachers told me that ALS completers usually entered senior high school with a definite lack of academic achievement relative to students in the regular curriculum. Basic literacy skills were perceived to have gaps, including an inability to read long texts, poor vocabulary, and poor writing in short paragraphs. In numeracy, it was also observed that even simple operations with whole numbers were difficult for some learners.

She further proposed that gaps related to subjects were also present especially in social studies where learners lacked any background knowledge and struggled to learn abstract concepts. Two participants put it very clearly when they commented that:

"I could see that there is some sort of learning gap compared to the regular students." (T3; PG.5; L 2-4). The biggest challenge I met was really the learning gap. It was difficult for them to adjust to the lessons." (T3; PG.5; L 15-20).

These made me reflect on how academic gaps significantly widen the instructional demands placed on teachers, requiring constant instructional adjustments to ensure that all learners, regardless of background, can follow and meaningfully engage with the lessons.

Considering the needs for instructional adjustment, one of my studied participants shared her experience in dealing such. She mentioned that her ALS learners commonly struggle with the pace and complexity of senior high school academic contents such as lessons in Social Sciences. She also shared how she modifies her instructional strategies through slowing down lesson delivery, simplifying complex concepts, and reteaching essential skills. Four of the participants said that:

"They need more help, especially in the instruction. Even the instruction itself needs to be explained further" (T7; PG14; L5-9), "There are terminologies that are not familiar for them" (T10; PG21; L56-57), "I need to go back and forth in my lesson... you go back to the basics" (T8; PG22; L1-4). "There is adjustment when it comes to delivery of activities.... They are not used to that kind of approach" (T2; PG27; L7-12).

Hearing their experiences, I realized that this continuous need for scaffolding reflects the reality that ALS learners are still catching up on fundamental competencies. This understanding led me to reflect more deeply on the teaching process, where I recognized that teachers must constantly adapt or simplify explanations, repeat instructions, and provide additional support to help learners cope with academic demands. However, I also acknowledge that addressing academic gap and instructional adjustment is insufficient. I need to consider learners' diverse needs and circumstances, which led me to the necessity of designing flexible teaching approaches that can respond to these needs.

Designing Flexible Teaching Approaches

After the review, I was guided with the idea of UDL to create teaching approach that will address learners' variability. In designing, two important aspects of teaching pedagogy may be considered, the flexibility and Equitability. Giving them equal access to support and opportunities. After designing this approach, I also recognized the need to implement it meaningfully in the classroom. However, the challenge is making it differentiated and supportive.

Implementing Differentiated and Supportive Pedagogical Design

After designing, I realized the need to implement it meaningfully. This realization led me to the idea of applying differentiated and supportive pedagogy. I never forget during the interview one teacher mentioned that he applies these principles. I never forget one participant mentioned that she pairs performing students with the low performing one to guide and assist them during lessons. I also remember another teacher mentioning that he provides extra time, extend explanations and targeted interventions to meet his students' diverse needs. Moreover, a teacher mentioned that to make her lessons more meaningful she connects it to real-life experiences. With these challenges three sub-themes exist namely pairing and peer support system, varying learning activities and interventions and applying lessons in real-life experiences.

Pairing and Peer Support Systems. During my conversations with the teachers, one of them mentioned that: "I need to guide them, and then I need to have a body-body... I partner them with students who are above average." (P1). Similar approach was also applied by three teachers saying that:

"I paired him, I assigned one classmate, one leader... a pairing system for him so that he can catch up" (T6; PG16; L18-23), "Pair group discussion... I can partner these students with those Achiever students" (T10; PG 23;

L30-33)., *“I paired ko, sa mga students na medyo higher ang intellect, sinasabi ko na, i-assist sila. (I paired them with students who are a bit more advanced intellectually, and I told them to assist the two.) (T1; PG28; L19-24).*

Listening to these challenges, I could see how intentional peer support not only helps ALS learners catch up academically but also builds their confidence and sense of belonging in the classroom. I also came to understand that this strategy not only helps to close the learning gaps, but also establish collaboration and a more welcoming and accommodating classroom setting to students. I acknowledge that teachers employed varied learning activities that transforms learners from being passive to active and participative one. Along the way, I also noticed that the varying techniques played an important rule in bridging learning gaps, shaping every learner to be collaborative and provide inclusive learning environment.

Varying Learning Activities and Interventions as supportive pedagogical design. Through my discussion with the teachers, varying learning activities and intervention is needed to meet the diverse needs of students. Applying varied learning activities Three of these teachers mentioned that:

Differentiated activity and differentiated instruction because every learner has different needs. (T2; PG12; L10-15, T5; PG10; L16-18, T10; PG32; L 20-24). Similar perspective was also shared by three teachers saying that:

I give them extra motion. I gave them extra time... I also give my spare time to explain. (T7; PG15; L20-25)., We need to provide more activities for them. We need to provide more illustrations, more examples... so that they can relate to their life. (T8; PG24; L6-12).

Reflecting on the teachers experiences above, I realized how much time and effort they invest to help their students understand the lesson. As another teacher mentioned that: *“I do interventions... I do casual updates” (T4; PG18; L2-5).* I realized how teachers actively monitor learners progress to provide ongoing support to student. I also understand that applying these varied instructional approaches enables students to understand and internalized the lessons well. As my study progress, I can see that there is a need to apply this lesson to real-life scenario to make learning more meaningful and relevant. Helping learners connect classroom knowledge to their personal experience and daily challenges.

Applying Lessons to real life experiences. It is an essential strategy to apply lessons to real-life experiences in teaching learners, as this helps lessons come alive and resonate more with learners. I remember one teacher said that:

Since social sciences... it would be better if you are going to use actual examples... that they have experience and they can relate to the topic’ (T2; PG11; L14-19).

It helps me see the value of connecting lessons to learners' real-life experiences.

I recall another teacher saying:

They make essays and reflect on themselves and... it has a significant impact on them(students) because they have already encountered such. (T4; PG19; L1-5).

In line with the provided experiences, I realized that the teacher was aware of the necessity to relate classroom tasks to the personal lives of students and help them learn the lesson using their own experiences and daily difficulties.

Reflecting on UDL-Driven Pedagogy

When educators discussed their experiences, they always had difficult situations associated with the differences among learners, academic discrepancies, and different life conditions. Nevertheless, they were not weakened in their efforts by these struggles. Teachers used creative and balanced strategies by employing the intentional use of flexible and equitable strategies that were founded on the UDL and transformed the challenges into significant teaching experiences. I noticed that the work was highly rewarding when watching the progress, growth, and engagement that people were having in the classroom, despite the complexity of the classroom.

Satisfying and gratifying amidst difficulty and complexity. When I talked to my participants individually, I was profoundly moved by the honesty of the teachers, who admitted that the variability of

learners expressed as academic disparity, discrepancy in learning capabilities, as well as varied life experiences, largely exacerbates the teaching experience. I recall three teachers, who spoke dejectedly saying:

“My experience was challenging because ALS students are not the same as the typical junior high.” (T1; PG 4; L10-13, T10; PG29; L1-5), “It’s a very challenging one, especially since most of the ALS completers are really, we call that, a bit behind in basic education.” (T7; PG15; L1-6), “I feel challenged because... Some are good, while others are not. So, I could feel challenged...” (T4; PG20; L10-13)

As I reflected with these experiences of teachers, I understand that this variability demands patience, flexibility, and a more personalized approach to ensure that all learners can progress despite their differences. Despite these challenges, I was deeply struck by the sense of fulfillment that my teacher participants expressed. I cannot forget four teachers described their genuine gratitude and compassion in their experiences saying:

“I feel happy because they were able to finish their senior high education and then proceeded to college.” (T1; PG30; L7-11), “It was really fulfilling because I realized that it’s not a hindrance to stop for some years and then decide to come back and study again.” (T; PG6; L18-22), “I’m grateful to teach them.” (T4; PG21; L3), “I feel more like a person who exudes help... we also need to extend our patience, our time.” (T7; PG16; L12-18).

Reflecting on these narratives, I agreed with the teachers that although handling ALS completers is challenging and complex, it is also deeply meaningful and gratifying. I see this progression as mirroring the UDL-based conceptual paradigm, where UDL is not merely an instructional framework but a guiding philosophy that shapes my adaptive practices, resilience, and sense of professional purpose in supporting every learner.

Discussions

In this chapter, I narrated the meaningful experiences of the people I conversed with in the field. I asserted the realizations I generated from those encounters vis-a-vis the ideas presented in previous studies. I stood firmly on academic gaps and instructional adjustments as outcomes of the reviews undertaken by my interviewees, pedagogical approaches they designed resulting from the gaps and adjustments and satisfying and gratifying amidst difficulty and complexity.

Academic Gaps and Instructional Adjustments

I was able to assert that variability does not automatically produce universal learning design. Reviewing the academic gaps and instructional adjustment is inevitable as basis for responding the variability. Based on this understanding, I agree with Canillo et al. (2024), who discovered that learning gaps and student performance were significantly related. Their research revealed that there were cognitive, motivational, and skills gaps among students in senior high schools and that broad-based interventions were required to ensure that learning was facilitated. These experiences demonstrated to me that peer support, diversified activities and real-life connections do benefit learners.

Pairing and Peer Support System

I realized this pedagogy as one of the most important strategies of arranging differentiation and supportive learning activities to improve collaboration and participation of learners. These lessons provide the significant approach to the insight into the means to create the classroom environment that will support inclusive learning, promote the sense of shared responsibility among the learners, and reinforce the engagement through the organized peer interactions. Based on these experiences, I can relate to the conclusion of Tian, Yu, and Huebner (2022), who considered the extent to which peer support encourages student engagement and participation.

Varying Learning Activities and Interventions as Supportive and Pedagogical Design

In my research, I noted that teachers modified teaching lessons by providing additional time, examples and concentrated explanations to help ALS learners. The observation of this practice made me understand that learners are able to actively engage with content and discern meaning in the lessons through flexible and customized instruction, which can justify UDL-based teaching strategies. This is in line with the fact that differentiated and diversified activities enhance engagement, motivation, and cognition (Salazar & Gumanoy, 2025). A second study also concluded that differentiated instruction is an effective approach in enhancing student motivation and engagement in the learning process in a variety of learning settings where learners indicated higher rates of interest and engagement when they could see that tasks were designed to meet their readiness and needs (Chenyang, 2023). Contrary to these results, I disagree with Gheysens et al. (2020), who discovered that teachers tend to use differentiated strategies fragmentedly by considering them as occasional methods, but not holistic pedagogical frameworks, which may restrain their potential to facilitate equitable learning design.

Applying Lessons to Real-life Experience

In my research, I was able to note that when lessons were related to the real-life experience of the students, learning became more significant. I felt the commitment of the teachers as I listened to them as they assisted the students in relating the lesson material to real life. This practice, in my opinion, made me aware of the fact that the only thing that makes learning meaningful and deep is meaningful real-life relationships. This agrees with recent studies that authentic learning leads to student engagement and understanding (Chang, Choi, & Şen-Akbulut, 2024).

Satisfying and Gratifying Amid Difficulty and Complexity

Although it was sometimes hard to reach the diverse learners, I felt it in the strong hold of their hands and the fire in their eyes when they told me how much they were satisfied to see their students make progress. This showed me how rewarding it is to support growth amid complexity. This experience aligns with the finding of Kazmi et.al. (2023), which indicate that teachers who hold positive attitudes towards inclusive practice tend to experience higher job satisfaction and professional commitment, reinforcing how supporting diverse learners and witnessing the progress can be deeply rewarding despite the challenges.

Implications for Practice

Based on my stated assertions in the earlier pages, I humbly recommend that teachers will conduct a review of the learning variability of their students before they are going to design the learning facilitation approaches or teaching styles. They may also consider not stopping at planning and designing of teaching strategies. Instead, continue valuing the processes they are undergoing for them to keep satisfied and gratified to survive challenges in teaching ALS completers.

Conclusion and Future Direction

Based on the results of my study, I am convinced that potential future research may be beneficial. This study may employ mediating analyses to explore how academic gaps mediate the relationship between persisting learner variability and designing flexible teaching approaches variables; and to investigate the mediating role of the implementation of differentiated and supportive pedagogical design on the correlation between flexible teaching approaches and valuing UDL-driven pedagogical design variables. Further, utilizing sub-themes emerging from my study as indicators of those variables of the mediating studies I proposed is recommended. Finally, an exploratory factor analysis may be pursued to develop robust instruments on these variables and indicators.

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